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***Woznikella triradiata* n. gen., n. sp. – a new kannemeyeriiform dicynodont from the Late Triassic of northern Pangea and the global distribution of Triassic dicynodonts**

**Tomasz SZCZYGIELSKI
Tomasz SULEJ**

Institute of Paleobiology, Polish Academy of sciences, Twarda 51/55, 00-818 Warsaw (Poland)
t.szczygielski@twarda.pan.pl
sulej@twarda.pan.pl

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On page 329, in Figure 19, the names of the following countries, Mozambique, Zambia, Australia and Antarctica, did not appear. Figure 19 is reproduced here, and the country names have been added. Appendix 15 has also been included in the article, to represent the phylogenetic matrix.

À la page 329, dans la Figure 19, les noms des pays suivants, Mozambique, Zambia, Australie, l'Antarctique, n'apparaissent pas. La Figure 19 est reproduite ici, et les noms des pays ont été ajoutés. L'Annexe 15 a également été incluse dans l'article, afin de représenter la matrice phylogénétique.

FIG. 19. — Estimated number of Triassic dicynodont species, including named taxa (solid colors in **A** and **B**) and specifically indeterminate finds that may reasonably represent new species based on lack of comparable named forms in the same formations (hatched in **A** and **B**): **A**, estimated number of species by age; **B**, estimated number of species by country across whole Triassic; **C**, per cent contribution of individual countries to estimated species diversity in time. Indeterminate occurrences obviously or likely belonging to known species (e.g., described as “cf.” when comparable species were already noted in the same formations or as “sp. indet.” but likely representing species already known from the same formations) excluded. “Anisian or younger” in **B** indicates species from formations of uncertain age historically correlated biostratigraphically with South African *Cynognathus* Assemblage Zone (see discussion in the text). For simplicity, these species were counted as Anisian in **C**. Stahleckeriid group includes Stahleckeriidae (Stahleckeriinae + Placeriinae) and taxa more closely related to the Stahleckeriidae than to the Kannemeyeriidae. Occurrences suggested by the ichnological record and ghost lineages not included.

APPENDIX 15. — Phylogenetic matrix. https://doi.org/10.5852/cr-palevol2023v22a17_s1